

NASA Preferred Reliability-Practices for Design and Test

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ABSTRACT

The diversity and relative autonomy of the NASA Field Centers fosters a situation where unnecessary repetition of design effort and the danger of loss of design techniques used for high reliability hardware is possible. Intercenter communication of technical approaches that have contributed to mission success reduces the chance for duplication of technical effort, provides a mechanism for retaining NASA's corporate knowledge in reliability, and promotes closer teamwork between the engineering and assurance communities.

NASA HQ established the NASA R&M Steering Committee (R&MSC) comprised of membership from each NASA Field Center. The primary charter of the R&MSC is to obtain, record, and share the best design practices that NASA has applied to successful space flight programs and current design considerations (guidelines) that should enhance flight reliability on emerging programs. The practices and guidelines are being assembled in a living document for distribution to NASA Centers and the aerospace community. The document will be updated annually with additional practices and guidelines as contributions from the Centers are reviewed and approved by the R&MSC. Practices and guidelines are not requirements but rather a means of sharing procedures and techniques that a given Center and the R&MSC together feel have strong technical merit and application to the design of space-related equipment. Many of these practices and guidelines also will have application to ground-based equipment, but the primary thrust is for space flight applications.

INTRODUCTION

The challenges of today's unmanned and manned space flight programs demands the most efficient use of our technical knowledge base. The nation's ability to meet the challenge of a permanent manned presence in space, and successfully execute future manned exploration of Mars presents an unparalleled challenge. An efficient reliability program will be absolutely essential for the nation's Civil Space Program to meet the challenges of the twenty-first century. To meet the challenge, NASA has undertaken an initiative to capture the design techniques that have contributed to mission

success on previous space flight programs. The benefits from this initiative are not only the development of technical memoranda shared throughout the Agency, but a genuine teamwork spirit that fosters technically objective communication between NASA Centers. Communication of best technical thought from collective Field Center experiences represents a major element upon which NASA will build the nation's future in space.

THE CHALLENGE FOR RELIABILITY DISCIPLINE

It has been over 20 years since man has landed on the moon. The mission objectives in the 1990s are significantly more challenging from both a technological and a programmatic standpoint. The success NASA has enjoyed during the 1960s, and the road map that was used to get there, are becoming increasingly obscure as many of the technical people in both NASA and the aerospace community become eligible for retirement. For example, in

FY 90, over 50 percent of the persons that left the Agency were in the age group that was predominant during the Apollo Program.¹ To complicate today's programmatic environment, the lack of wide-based public support enjoyed during the Apollo days and the continued tightening of the Federal budget present additional challenges for the nation's Civil Space Program. The erosion of our corporate knowledge coupled with

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budgetary and political pressures has placed programs such as Space Station Freedom and Space Shuttle on a stringent success-oriented path where failures cannot be tolerated. The challenge is simple and straightforward: maintain a disciplined focus on the engineering fundamentals that control frequency of failure or have a reduced presence in space. The challenge requires a total team effort involving management, engineering, and the assurance disciplines.

The days when the scope of the reliability effort could be restricted to critique of a design after key design decisions have been made, or limiting reliability assurance activities to Failure Modes and Effects Analysis and probabilistic analysis to assess the risk of flying with a given design, are over. The Reliability Assurance discipline must expand its horizons to include an independent set of eyes that will examine key facets of a sound system engineering process. This set of eyes should view environmental requirements definitions, engineering analysis results, test planning, interface control documentation, and more. Further, this independent set of eyes must focus attention on design details with technical credibility and in a timely and technically credible manner to identify and support redesign efforts to fix problems early rather than develop a compendium of technical rationale to fly as is.

The engineering process within NASA and the aerospace community has become more sophisticated within the past 30 years. Our engineering capability has increased by orders of magnitude. Our understanding of failure mechanisms in electronics devices and current use of computerized workstations and simulations attest to that fact. Use of computer-aided engineering (CAE) workstations can integrate results of stress analysis, failure rate data, and performance parameters to optimize system configurations. The product development process in both the commercial sector and DOD is embracing a concurrent engineering process that integrates R&M with performance requirements. Demanding system requirements and the

expanding complexity and cost of our space flight systems introduces high technical risk. It is the risk — the consequence of overlooking an apparently small detail on ever increasing complex and expensive systems — that has changed. The public's confidence has quickly eroded due to the stringent Federal budget, the consequences of delays in Shuttle launch, an unsuccessful assembly or maintenance mission on-orbit, or unexpected performance anomalies that degrade performance on major flight programs. Any on-orbit repair mission is extremely expensive, especially with one-of-a-kind replacement components. The estimated \$40- to \$50-million dollar repair cost² for Hubble Space Telescope (HST) is a cost data point for an on-orbit repair of a complex system. The high cost of repair and the understandably tight Federal budget constraints are quickly making the recovery costs for technical error an unacceptable option.

The challenge to all involved in the nation's Civil Space Program, now more than ever before, is "that we design, test, and build it right the first time." It is the new external environment within which we live that demands the need to have a second opinion on the technical aspects that affect the design and fabrication of our increasingly complex spacecraft. It is this second opinion that must be assumed by the R&M assurance community within NASA and the aerospace industry. The Reliability Best Practices initiative provides a technical foundation for this second opinion.

THE TECHNICAL CAPABILITY WITHIN NASA

Two years ago, a fundamental question posed by the Associate Administrator for Safety and Mission Quality was: "Are we within the assurance discipline doing all that we should be doing to assure the highest practical degree of mission success?" The NASA R&MSC was established to assure that the answer is yes. The Steering Committee includes representatives from Ames Research Center, Goddard Space Flight Center, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, Kennedy Space Center, Lewis Research Center, Marshall Space Flight Center, and the Johnson Space Center. The Committee expressed concern that the reliability discipline must be strengthened if NASA is to meet the demands of the twenty-first century. Careful attention to cause and effect relationships of failure modes is an effective approach for relatively short-duration missions where on-orbit assembly, maintenance, and resupply are not factors. Analytical techniques such as fault trees and failure modes and effects must be augmented by a disciplined review of technical requirements, engineering analysis, test results, and interface documentation to assure that the configuration of our space flight systems possess two key characteristics: (1) the ability to operate within its prescribed stress environment, and (2) the ability to be assembled/disassembled efficiently on-orbit. Overemphasis on cause

and effect analysis for programs (such as Space Station Freedom, lunar bases, manned Mars missions or similar long-duration man-accessible missions) where maintenance and resupply is both a technical and a cost factor demand extremely careful attention to the design details that affect frequency of failure and ease of assembly/repair. It is this extra careful attention to detail that NASA envisions as the joint responsibility of program management, engineering functions, and assurance functions. R&M Assurance provides an independent set of eyes to serve as a double check that our highly complex spacecraft are able to perform their missions, as intended, with a minimum of maintenance and logistics burden (i.e., mission quality).

Technical experience that has contributed to previous successful space flight missions is the cornerstone from which management, engineering, and assurance should base their technical assessments. The wide range of NASA missions, from aeronautics research to manned space flight, fosters an ideal situation to identify different technical approaches. The Reliability Best Practices Initiative was undertaken to document the best technical thought on reliability-related topics.

NASA recently has released the second edition of the publication "NASA Reliability Preferred Practices for Design and Test" (proven practices from successful NASA programs plus guidelines with unique applications). The document is a series of memoranda on various reliability topics. The memoranda are divided into two major categories (practices and guidelines). A practice identifies a particular requirement, analytical, or test approach that in the judgement of the sponsoring Field Center has contributed to

mission success on a space flight program. A guideline addresses the same topics as a practice; however, its contribution to mission success on a space flight program has not yet been demonstrated. Contained in the preliminary publication are 13 practices/guidelines. An additional 11 practices recently have been endorsed by the NASA R&MSC for publication. NASA currently plans to issue supplemental practices annually.

Although a broad range of topics are covered, the central theme is clear: establish technical requirements that design a configuration that will withstand the stresses contained in the operating environment, fabricate the systems and subsystems such that the tolerance drift expected over a long time duration will not contribute to frequency of failure, and use the best quality parts. The principles are nothing new. However, NASA's experience base from a wide range of aeronautics and space projects has been integrated in the Practices document to identify the best technical opinion. The topics include nonelectronic space flight issues such as magnetic design practices, meteoroid/space debris design, as well as environmental requirements and design and test criteria for electronics assemblies (topics that have been discussed thoroughly for years). The practices are

intended to both document proven techniques and those at the cutting edge. The current edition strives to capture the proven material before it is lost. Future issues will begin to emphasize the unproven material.

THE APPROACH USED FOR RESEARCHING PRACTICES AND GUIDELINES

Any NASA Center may submit a topic for technical consideration. In addition to a brief statement of the practice or guideline, the technical discussion on each topic must address the following key topics:

- (1) **Benefit:** A concise statement of the technical improvement realized from implementing the practice.
- (2) **Program That Certified Use:** Identifiable programs or projects that have applied the subject technique (guidelines do not require this item to be included).
- (3) **Implementation Method:** A brief technical discussion for use that is not intended to give full details of the process, but rather provides the reader with adequate information to understand how the practice or guideline should be used.
- (4) **Center to Contact for More Information:** Source(s) of additional technical information on the specific practice or guideline.
- (5) **Technical Rationale:** A brief technical justification for the use of the practice or guideline.
- (6) **Impact of Nonpractice:** A brief statement of the technical consequences if the practice or guideline is not used.
- (7) **Related Practices/Guidelines:** A ready reference to related practices / guidelines.

The NASA R&MSC serves as the focal point to coordinate internal Center reviews on all topics submitted for consideration. Steering Committee meetings are held quarterly to review and baseline the proposed topics. A minimum of 30 days before the Steering Committee meeting, each member receives a complete set of the practices and guidelines. The member distributes these internally to his/her Center's expertise in the appropriate technical area. Technical comments and opinions on topics reviewed are presented by each Steering Committee member.

During the development of many of the practices and guidelines, there have been strong differences of technical opinion. The technical discussions on the Thermal Cycling and Junction Temperatures Practices are two examples where strong differing opinions were expressed. Notwithstanding the existence of differing technical approaches within NASA, it has been possible to reach a consensus that has permitted publication of practices and guidelines on controversial topics. It is the open discussion forum of the R&MSC meetings that has been so essential to ensuring that the opinion stated in a practice or guideline represent the best technical thinking that the Agency has to offer on a particular topic.

This open and frank discussion has been greatly aided by one major ground rule: *No practice or guideline shall be imposed as a technical requirement.* The practices published shall serve as technical memoranda to document processes and procedures that have worked. The technical memoranda should be used in three ways. First, the program or project manager has a consistent technical basis upon which to evaluate risk at specific design and development milestones (i.e., Preliminary Design Review, Critical Design Review). Because the practices and guidelines are based on previous experience, the more differences observed between the criteria presented in these practices and the approaches being taken by an individual project or program are indications of technical risk. Second, the design engineer can gain important insight into requirements, processes, and procedures that had a pay-off in similar applications. Although an individual practice is not a detailed treatise on a subject, information is provided where an engineer can obtain additional technical details in an area of interest. Third, the assurance specialist now has a starting point from which he confidently can be a technically credible and independent set of eyes in executing his/her assurance role.

The publication is scheduled for annual supplements. Table 1 identifies the topics that are being investigated and will be considered for inclusion in the next supplement.

Table 1
Reliability Practices & Guidelines Topics

Initial Issue:

- Environmental Factors
- EEE Parts Derating
- High Voltage Power Supply Design
- Class S Parts in High Reliability Applications
- Surface Charging and Electrostatic Discharge Analysis
- EEE Parts Screening
- Thermal Cycling
- Thermographic Mapping of Printed Circuit Boards
- Thermal Test Levels
- Powered on Vibration
- Sinusoidal Vibration
- Earth Orbit Environmental Heating (Guideline)

Supplemental Issue:

- Assembly Acoustic Testing
- Magnetic Design Practices for Scientific Instruments
- Welding of Aerospace Hardware (for 2219 aluminum and Inconel 718)
- Pyrotechnic Shock
- Power Line Filters
- Thermal Vacuum Versus Thermal Atmospheric Test
- Risk Rating of Problem/Failure Reports

The one untapped resource that would add immeasurable value to improving reliability technology within the aerospace community is the aerospace industry. Design criteria on liquid and solid propulsion systems is a particular void that currently is being researched. Industry participation is strongly encouraged. Table 2 identifies members of the NASA R&MSC. Those aerospace contractor's that desire to make a contribution should contact the appropriate Field Center directly through the Steering Committee member. The companies participating in the program automatically are placed on distribution for subsequent publications.

Table 2
NASA R&MSC Members
(Effective September 25, 1991)

Ames Research Center:	Dan Lee
Goddard Space Flight Center:	Jack Remez
Jet Propulsion Laboratory:	Tom Gindorf
Johnson Space Center:	Nancy Steisslinger
Kennedy Space Center:	Leon Migdalski
Lewis Research Center:	Vincent Lalli
Marshall Space Flight Center:	Donald Bush
NASA Headquarters:	Ronald C. Lisk, Chairman

WHAT'S THE VALUE?

The aerospace community now has a means for judging technical risk based on a compendium of technical experience. The practices and guidelines were formatted intentionally for understanding by engineering, management, and the assurance disciplines. Each practice or guideline is not an exhaustive treatise on a subject but is structured to provide sufficient information to evaluate technical merit for application to a particular project or program. The compendium of practices/guidelines can serve as an indicator of technical risk. Because the practices are based on actual design experiences, the more practices that are not included as part of a project's way of doing business, the greater the technical risk. Finally, NASA's Reliability Preferred Practices for Design and Test may serve as a conduit for inter-center communication between NASA Field Centers on using techniques that have served the wide-spectrum of NASA projects well. This communication of technical experience, irrespective of some dynamic differences in technical opinion, fosters a teamwork approach in the true spirit of Total Quality Management (TQM). Whether a TQM approach is executed through a formal concurrent engineering program or through open and frank communication between an entire organization, the bottom

line is teamwork. It will be the team approach that will sustain NASA and the nation as technical leaders in space exploration.

REFERENCES

1. "The Civil Service Work Force Fiscal Year 1990;" NASA Office of Management and Human Resources.
2. Information quoted by NASA in November 28, 1990, issue of Aerospace Daily; pg 339.

BIOGRAPHY

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Mr. Lisk is the Manager of Reliability & Maintainability (R&M) in the Office of the Associate Administrator for Safety and Mission Quality. He is responsible for Agency-wide R&M policy, participates directly on Shuttle recertification reviews and on preliminary design reviews for Space Station Freedom, and has developed assessments of the merits of probabilistic risk assessment techniques for NASA programs. Prior to NASA, he worked with the RM&QA Directorate, Naval Material Command, on initiatives associated with the Defense Science Board Task Force recommendations for technical risk reduction in the weapons system development and acquisition process. He contributed significantly to DOD Directive 4245.7 and to "Best Practices for Transitioning from Development to Production." Mr. Lisk has a BSEE from the University of Detroit, and an MS in Public Administration from the University of Northern Colorado.